

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

Hong Dzung Lai

Farida Yunusovna Akhmadullina

Rustem Kayumovich Zakirov

Department of Industrial Biotechnology, Kazan National Research Technological University, Kazan, Russia

Renat Maratovich Akhmadullin

R&D Center "AkhmadullinS" LLC, Kazan, Russia

Quoc Bao Tran

Ho Chi Minh City University of Natural Resource and Environment; Vietnam

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INVESTIGATION OF THE ACTIVITY OF HETEROGENEOUS CATALYST CONTAINING METAL OXIDE ON HEAT-RESISTANT POLYMER (POLYPHENYLENE SULFIDE)

Abstract.

This study summarizes the catalytic activity of some metal oxides immobilized on a thermostable polymer (polyphenylene sulfide) in sulfide oxidation at high temperature and pressure. The experiments were carried out in a titanium autoclave with high sulfide concentrations up to 3 wt% sulfur. The activity of the catalysts was evaluated based on the sulfide removal efficiency as well as the reaction time. The results showed that metal oxides had high catalytic activity, increasing the reaction rate and decreasing the oxidation time. Among the catalysts investigated, the catalyst containing MnO₂ was shown to be the most effective with the ability to remove 86% of sulfide within 10 minutes. This study contributes an effective method to treat wastewater with high sulfide concentration, thereby contributing to solving the water pollution problem in some industries.

Keywords: *Heterogeneous catalyst, sulfide-alkali wastewater, oxidation, wastewater treatment, polyphenylene sulfide, catalytic activity.*

INTRODUCTION

The growing industries have created a huge amount of wastewater containing organic and inorganic pollutants, directly affecting health as well as the surrounding ecosystem. A challenging problem is posed to effectively treat this wastewater. In particular, sulfide-alkali wastewater (SAW) generated from industries such as, petrochemical refining, dyeing processes using sulfur dyes, pulp production, etc. has become significant concern for environmental managers [1-4]. Such wastewater types are characterized by high toxicity, unpleasant odor and high corrosiveness to metal and concrete surfaces [5]. Moreover, in the case of wastewater with low sulfide content, biological oxidation is applied with the participation of microorganisms to decompose inorganic and organic sulfur into less toxic or harmless products. Several strong oxidizing agents have been used to remove sulfide such as H₂O₂, KMnO₄, NaClO etc. However, treating high sulfide concentrations increases costs due to the use of large amounts of reagents and can directly affect the environment [6]. Currently, oxidation methods with heterogeneous catalysts are receiving more attention due to their regenerative ability, efficiency and safety. Heterogeneous catalysts have been developed with diverse active components (pyrolusite ore, phthalocyanine and its derivatives; transition metal oxides) immobilized on supports such as clay, low-temperature working polymers (such as low-density polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene) [7-9]. However, the use of these supports leads to catalysts that often operate at low temperatures and have low oxidation capacity when treating wastewater containing high concentrations of sulfide. Therefore, improving

catalysts to meet the needs of sulfide waste treatment is extremely necessary.

In this study, polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) was used as a novel support materials to synthesize catalysts based on metal oxides acting as active components. The aim of the study was to investigate the activity of the targeted catalysts in the liquid-phase oxidation of concentrated sulfide under high temperature and pressure conditions. The research results have provided a new direction for treating wastewater containing high sulfide.

EXPERIMENTAL-ANALYTICAL METHODS

Materials. In this study, high purity chemicals were used including; manganese oxides (MnO, Mn₂O₃, MnO₂), copper oxides (CuO, Cu₂O); titanium (IV) oxide (TiO₂); iron (III) oxide (Fe₂O₃); Nickel oxide (NiO), (chromium (III) oxide (Cr₂O₃); lead (II) oxide (PbO); cadmium (II) oxide (CdO), Sodium Sulfide (Na₂Sx9H₂O) and polyphenylene sulfide (Center "AkhmadullinS" LLC, Kazan, Russia).

Methods. Quantitative inorganic sulfide content before and after oxidation was determined by potentiometric titration method UOP-209-00 [10].

Experimental setup. The oxidation was carried out in an autoclave (250 ml) placed on a magnetic stirrer and oxygen was added from an oxygen cylinder. The reaction continued until the pressure in the autoclave became constant.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

During the study, 11 heterogeneous catalysts were synthesized with metal oxides as active materials (MnO₂, Mn₂O₃, MnO, CuO, Cu₂O, Fe₂O₃, TiO₂, CdO,

PbO, NiO, Cr₂O₃) and polymer (Polyphenylene sulfide) as support matrix. The ratio between metal oxide and PPS was investigated as 20:80. The sulfide oxidation reaction was carried out in a closed reactor, at a temperature of 200 °C, a pressure of 3.65 Mpa and a stir-

ring speed of 1000 rpm. In addition, to evaluate the catalytic activity, the liquid phase oxidation of sulfide was conducted in the presence and absence of catalysts. The research results are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Catalytic activity of heterogeneous catalysts in liquid phase oxidation of sulfide.

From the experimental results in Fig. 1, it can be seen that the presence of heterogeneous catalysts containing metal oxides accelerates the sulfide conversion process and reduces the reaction time compared to the blank experiment. Additionally, it can be easily seen that the shortest time of liquid phase sulfide oxidation is observed when using a heterogeneous catalyst based on MnO₂. The use of this catalyst reduces the oxidation time of sulfide by 5 times compared to the oxidation process without catalyst. Some metal oxides also such as Fe₂O₃, MnO, Mn₂O₃, TiO₂, CuO and NiO also show high efficiency with oxidation times reaching about 14 minutes. In addition, the highest sulfide removal efficiency is also observed in the presence of these catalysts. Of these, the catalyst with manganese oxide (IV) achieved the highest efficiency of 86% while the remaining catalyst's efficiency ranged from 76-79%.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the presented heterogeneous catalysts have high catalytic activity in the oxidation of inorganic sulfide. Under high temperature and pressure conditions the manganese oxide (IV) catalyst was proven to be the most effective with sulfide reduction

efficiency reaching 86% within 10 minutes. The investigation outcome show the applicability of heterogeneous catalysts containing metal oxides on PPS platform to achieve high efficiency, saving time and cost for the treatment of wastewater containing sulfide at high concentrations.

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